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Annotatsiya: Maqolada xalq qo‘shiq-lari yosh avlodni ma’naviy va axloqiy tarbiyalashda tutgan beqiyos o‘rni tahlil etiladi. Xalq qo‘shiq-lari qadimdan yoshlarning ruhiy olamini boyitish, milliy qadriyat va an’analarni singdirish, badiiy-estetik didni shakllantirishda asosiy vositalardan biri bo‘lib kelgan. Tadqiqotda xalq qo‘shiq-larining tarbiyaviy ta’sir mexanizmlari: emotsional identifikatsiya, milliy g‘urur uyg‘otish, qadriyatlarni ongli ravishda qabul qilish va ijtimoiy birdamlikni mustahkamlash kabi omillar ilmiy asosda tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy ta’lim va tarbiya jarayonida xalq musiqiy merosidan samarali foydalanish bo‘yicha taklif va tavsiyalar ilgari suriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Xalq qo‘shiq-lari, ma’naviy tarbiya, axloqiy qadriyatlar, estetik ta’lim, badiiy tafakkur, milliy o‘zlik, yoshlar tarbiyasi, musiqa tarbiyasi.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется уникальная роль народных песен в духовно-нравственном воспитании подрастающего поколения. Народные песни издавна служили мощным средством обогащения внутреннего мира молодежи, привития национальных ценностей и традиций, формирования художественно-эстетического вкуса. В исследовании научно обоснованы механизмы воспитательного воздействия народных песен, такие как эмоциональная идентификация, пробуждение национальной гордости, осознанное принятие ценностей и укрепление социальной солидарности. Также предлагаются рекомендации по эффективному использованию музыкального народного наследия в современных образовательных и воспитательных процессах.

Ключевые слова: Народные песни, духовное воспитание, нравственные ценности, эстетическое образование, художественное мышление, национальная идентичность, воспитание молодежи, музыкальное воспитание.

Annotation: This article explores the unique role of folk songs in the spiritual and moral upbringing of the younger generation. Historically, folk songs have served as a powerful medium for enriching young people's inner world, instilling national values and traditions, and cultivating artistic and aesthetic taste. The study provides a scientific analysis of the educational impact mechanisms of folk songs, including emotional identification, the awakening of national pride, the conscious acceptance of values, and the strengthening of social cohesion. Additionally, the article offers recommendations for the effective use of folk musical heritage in modern educational and upbringing processes.

Key words: Folk songs, spiritual education, moral values, aesthetic education, artistic thinking, national identity, youth upbringing, music education.

Folk songs are a rare spiritual source that reflects the spiritual world, historical experience and social life of each nation. In the musical culture of the Uzbek people, folk songs have played an important role not only as a means of providing aesthetic pleasure, but also as a means of spiritual education, the formation of moral values, and the expression of social life. The songs created in the oral art of our people and passed down from generation to generation glorify such high qualities as humanity, patriotism, hard work, kindness, and justice. In today's era of globalization and cultural integration, a

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deep analysis of the spiritual and social essence of Uzbek folk songs and their inculcation in the minds of the younger generation is considered an urgent task.

The main idea of Uzbek folk songs is to purify the human soul, encourage it to goodness and goodness. Human relationships, moral and spiritual values are very richly expressed in our national songs.

Loyalty and love: In folk songs, the pure feelings of human love, loyalty, and devotion occupy a central place.

Patriotism: In folk songs such as “O Motherland”, “My Song is Mine”, the ideas of praising the homeland and sacrificing for the homeland are dominant.

Moral lessons: Qualities such as respect for parents, respect for teachers, friendship and solidarity are taught as spiritual lessons in many folk songs.

Spiritual message: Since the advice given through folk songs is simple, practical and easily accepted, they are firmly established in the minds of the people.

Social ideas and their expression. Reflecting the socio-political conditions of their time, folk songs expressed the hopes, dreams, pains and aspirations of the people, and their dissatisfaction with social injustices.

Glorification of labor: In songs such as “Dehqon koshig‘I” and “Gozapoya”, the life of a hardworking person and his labor in harmony with nature are praised. These songs depict the lives of peasants and artisans as positive characters.

Social equality and justice: Some folk songs are an expression of popular discontent against tyrannical rulers. For example, the epics “Kokaldosh” and “Oshiq Gharib” promote the ideas of fighting oppression and injustice.

The status of women and family values: The image of women as loving mothers and devoted wives occupies a special place in folk songs.

Folk songs are a product of the spiritual world, historical memory and social consciousness of the nation. They were created not only for artistic pleasure, but also served the purpose of spiritual education, instilling moral norms and strengthening unity in society. Folk songs have their own mechanisms of influencing human thinking, and they have been shaping the psyche of generations for centuries.

Folk songs are a means of conveying an educational message to people, not through direct intellectual and theoretical propaganda, but through spiritual and emotional influence. They shape the human soul directly, in a way that is assimilated at the subconscious level. In this respect, folk songs:

- A carrier of moral values,
- A source of national identity and pride,
- Performs the functions of an artistic expression of the life experience of society.

Historical context: Uzbek folk songs were created in accordance with the spiritual needs of their time. Therefore, they retain their relevance over time.

Emotional-spiritual impact. The melody, musical structure and text of songs directly affect the human heart. Because:

- Songs evoke emotions through intonation and rhythm.
- Through lyrical images, they encourage people to feelings such as sympathy, love, and selflessness.
- The harmony of music and words is easily retained in memory, as a result, the impact on behavior increases.

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Example: In songs like “O Motherland”, the spirit of selflessness for the motherland and love for the homeland is strong and inspires the listener.

The images given in folk songs (peasant, lovers, selfless young men, loving mother, etc.) serve as a social ideal for young listeners.

- Young people compare themselves to the hero in the song.
- They form qualities such as goal-orientedness, courage, loyalty, and patience.

Example: In the song fragments of the epic poem “Gorugli”, the idea of courage and justice is strongly praised. Issues of instilling traditional values at the subconscious level. Folk songs have an indirect effect: through them, advice and education are secretly, imperceptibly absorbed into the minds of children and young people. Values that are freely accepted without external coercion are firmly established in the mind. As a cultural code, folk songs are continuously passed from older to younger generations. Example: In the song “Kaldirgoch”, love for motherly love and nature are instilled.

Folk songs are of incomparable importance in the formation of the spiritual maturity, aesthetic taste and sense of national identity of the younger generation. Their psycho-emotional impact, the mechanism of identification through ideal heroes and the ability to instill cultural traditions at the subconscious level make them a powerful educational tool. Today, the full use of the educational potential of folk songs, their introduction to the consciousness of the younger generation in modern forms remains an important factor in the development of national culture and spirituality.

Uzbek folk songs are also distinguished by their educational function:

Instilling moral values: Through folk songs, young people have learned such qualities as patriotism, kindness, patience, and honesty.

Preservation of spiritual heritage through oral tradition: Songs have been passed down from teacher to student, from mother to child, forming the common cultural memory of the people.

Strengthening unity and solidarity in society: Uzbek folk songs have always served as a means of uniting society and gathering people around a common goal. Awareness of identity: Folk songs have played an important role in the formation of national identity, national pride, and cultural identity.

Modern interpretation of folk songs and their promotion among young people. Today, modern approaches are needed to popularize folk songs among young people:

Folklore ensembles and national festivals: Folk songs are widely promoted within the framework of international festivals such as "Sharq Taronalari".

Use of digital technologies: Special channels for folk songs have been opened on platforms such as YouTube and Spotify, and they are being popularized among young people.

Modernization and adaptation: Some artists are reinterpreting national songs with modern musical styles and creating projects that appeal to young people (for example, remixes, the electro-folk genre).

Teaching national music in school and higher education programs: Teaching folk songs and national songs in music education can develop national culture and spirituality in the minds of young people.

Uzbek folk songs are an expression of the spiritual wealth, spiritual heritage and historical memory of our people. The spiritual and social ideas contained in them are of incomparable importance in the development of every Uzbek child, in the formation of his consciousness and thinking. By studying folk songs and promoting them in modern conditions, we can educate our youth to be loyal to national culture, spiritually mature, worthy of world civilization. Therefore, it is our spiritual duty to carefully approach the heritage of folk songs, to study it, develop it and pass it on in harmony with the times.

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